

Interview with Health Care Professionals, after experiment:

Overall instructions for interviewers:

- Explain the purpose of the interview:
 - o To gather information about their experience with the PAL system
 - o To use this information to change and improve the PAL system
 - o It is not a test, so no wrong or right answers and criticism (if you did not like something, or like to see something improved) is greatly valued
- Ask for permission to audio tape the conversation
- Try to complete the following questionnaire with the health care professional.
- Encourage the health care professional to elaborate, and try to think of follow up questions, especially when the answer is not clear (write down the main aspects of their answer)

Interview questions

- Did the child/children achieve their goals? If not, why not?
- What was the role of the parents and your own role? Did you have to motivate or assist the child actively?
- Do you think that the PAL robot (both the robot in the hospital, and the robot on the children's mobile phone/tablet) is useful for children with diabetes to manage diabetes every day? Why yes/no?
- Do you think that the PAL robot helped the children to be more actively involved in their diabetes?
- Do you think the children felt supported by the PAL robot in dealing with their diabetes?
- Do you think the children liked and trusted the robot? How do you think they perceive him? Eg. as a friend or a teacher?
- Did the robot help you to talk to children about their diabetes? How?
- Would the PAL robot help you in the care you/your hospital provide for children with diabetes?
- In your opinion, what aspects of the robot worked best?
- What aspects of the robot need improvement? What would you change?
- Can you think of additional features of the robot that will make him more appealing or more useful for children?
- Do you think children will stay motivated to continue using the system?
- Was the PAL system easy for you to work with?
- Do you have sufficient time and knowledge to work with the PAL system?
- Do you trust the PAL system? Why?

- Do you see the PAL robot as an improvement of the care that is provided for children with diabetes? Why?
- In your opinion, is the PAL system competitive with the other devices that are already used? Why?
- Where do you see the opportunities of the PAL system?
- Would you continue to use it? If not, what needs to be changed for you to continue to work with the system?

System Usability Scale (© Digital Equipment Corporation, 1986)

Could you please indicated in which degree you agree with the following statements:

Strongly disagree – 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Strongly agree

(consider to print this scale out and put it on the table or let them complete it)

1. I think that I would like to use the PAL system frequently
2. I found the PAL system unnecessarily complex
3. I thought the PAL system was easy to use
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use the PAL system
5. I found the various functions in the PAL system were well integrated
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in the PAL system
7. I would imagine that most people, for example other health care professionals, would learn to use the PAL system very quickly
8. I found the PAL system very cumbersome to use
9. I felt very confident using the PAL system
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the PAL system

Finishing up:

Do you have anything to add or any comments to make?